

A novel synthesis pathway for oxide dispersion strengthened Fe–Cr alloys enabled by ultrasonic atomization

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Abstract

1 This study introduces an innovative manufacturing approach for oxide dispersion strengthened (ODS)
2 alloys that employs ultrasonic atomization (UA) as the key processing step. A ferritic ODS alloy with
3 the composition Fe-14Cr-0.4Ti-0.5Y (wt.%) was prepared by arc melting and suction casting, using
4 either elemental yttrium or a Fe₂Y master alloy as the Y source. This was followed by UA under
5 continuous Ar flow. The residual O in the gas flow during atomization is sufficient allow for the
6 formation of Y₄₂Ti₁₀O₄₅ dispersoids by nucleation and growth from the supersaturated liquid.
7 Microhardness measurements of consolidated samples exhibit values comparable to those obtained
8 through conventional mechanical alloying and sintering, demonstrating UA as a promising alternative
9 for ODS alloy fabrication.

Keywords

10 ODS steel, ultrasonic atomization, powder metallurgy, dispersoids, atom probe tomography

1. Introduction

11 Fe-based oxide dispersion strengthened (ODS) alloys have been promising candidates for high
12 temperature and nuclear applications. These alloys can be further subdivided into ferritic [1–4] and
13 austenitic alloys [5,6]. Their use in fission and fusion reactor applications is attributed to their excellent
14 swelling resistance, ability to reduce point defect concentration by trapping irradiation induced
15 vacancies, and good irradiation creep resistance [1–4,7,8]. Additionally, they possess remarkable room
16 temperature (RT) strength and excellent creep resistance above 600 °C [1,2,9–11]. The addition of Ti to
17 the alloy composition promotes the formation of extremely fine Y-Ti-O nanoparticles, typically in the
18 size range of 2–5 nm, in contrast to Ti-free ODS alloys, where the oxide particles are coarser, ranging
19 from 20 to 200 nm. These Y-Ti-O mixed oxides are commonly known as *nanoclusters* [12,10]. The
20 dispersed nanoclusters effectively hinder dislocation motion by pinning dislocations [13,14], which
21 enhances material's strength, work hardening ability, high temperature creep resistance and eventually
22 even ductility [11,15,16]. However, coarsening of these dispersoids reduces their effectiveness in
23 hindering dislocations due to increased interparticle spacing [17,18]. Besides their direct impact on
24 strengthening, they can also act as pinning centers for grain boundaries, thereby suppressing grain
25 growth and resulting in finer grains (compared to non-ODS counterparts), which contributes to Hall-
26 Petch strengthening [13,16,19,20].

27 Historically, ODS alloys were manufactured via powder metallurgy routes, which include mechanical
28 alloying (MA) as the crucial processing step [2,5,6]. This utilizes high-energy ball milling of metal
29 powders mixed with fine oxide particles (typically Y_2O_3). The process involves repeated cold welding,
30 fracturing, and rewelding of the metal powder particles, while the Y_2O_3 particles are simultaneously
31 fragmented and dispersed throughout the matrix [21]. When Ti is present, Y-O-Ti clusters already form
32 during milling and evolve further during consolidation through sequential enrichment in Ti and Y,
33 ultimately forming thermally stable $Y_2Ti_2O_7$ nano-oxides at consolidation temperatures around
34 1100 °C [22]. These powders produced by MA are then typically consolidated via hot
35 extrusion (HE) [23,24], hot isostatic pressing (HIP) [25,26], or field assisted sintering
36 technique (FAST) [5,6,18,27]. Despite of its wide adaptation for powder production [21,28–30], the MA
37 route has some critical drawbacks, namely a substantial O and N pickup as well as wear debris from
38 balls and container during ball milling [31,32]. Higher O and N content can potentially have a
39 detrimental effect on the ductility. For example, increasing the O content from 0.04 to 0.16 wt.% in an
40 Fe-22Cr-5Al ODS alloy leads to the formation of stripe and chain precipitates near grain boundaries
41 causing partial intergranular fracture and reduced ductility [33]. Inhomogeneous oxide distribution due
42 to various processing related reasons is another drawback of the MA process, which negatively affects
43 the mechanical properties in ODS Fe-Cr alloys [32,34].

44 To mitigate the drawbacks of classical MA routes, a novel synthesis route to produce ODS alloys is
45 proposed in the present work. In this method, elemental Y is used to form dispersoids by oxidation
46 instead of using Y_2O_3 powder in the production of the ODS alloy. Since most of the ferritic alloys
47 described earlier are Fe-Cr based, with a Cr concentration between 13–14 wt.%, the Cr content in the
48 alloy studied here is set to 14 wt.%. Ti is added to probe if this process can potentially form Y-Ti-O
49 nanoclusters. ODS powder produced by MA mentioned earlier has a Y_2O_3 concentration of 0.25–
50 0.5 wt.% [1–4]. We, therefore, set the Y content in the alloy to 0.5 wt.% and the final composition is
51 Fe-14Cr-0.4Ti-0.5Y (wt.)/Fe-15Cr-0.5-0.3Y (at.%).

52 This study aims to answer the following research questions:

- 53 1. Is it thermodynamically and kinetically possible to form Y-Ti-O nanocluster dispersoids
54 through internal oxidation of Y during or after ultrasonic atomization?
- 55 2. At which stage of the processing route do dispersoids form and what is the mechanism behind
56 the formation of these dispersoids?
- 57 3. Do the dispersoids form uniformly with respect to chemical composition, size and spatial
58 distribution?
- 59 4. How do the mechanical properties of ultrasonically atomized ODS alloys compare to
60 mechanically alloyed counterparts from literature?

2. Materials and experimental methodology

2.1 Material synthesis

61 During the initial arc melting stage, two distinct synthesis approaches were employed to cast the alloy;
62 one utilizing elemental Y and the other employing a Fe₂Y master alloy. This manuscript primarily
63 focuses on the processing route involving elemental Y, while results for the Fe₂Y master alloy route
64 (referred to as ODS-Fe₂Y) are provided in the Supplementary Material Figure S1.

65 The alloys were synthesized through repetitive arc melting on a water-cooled copper mold in an Ar
66 (99.998 % purity) atmosphere using an AM/0.5 furnace (Edmund Bühler GmbH, Germany). The
67 purities of the constituents (Fe, Cr, Ti, and Y/Fe₂Y) were 99.95 %. The arc-melted buttons were then
68 drop cast into cylindrical rods of 10 mm diameter and 120 mm height in a water-cooled suction mold.
69 The rods were further used for ultrasonic atomization (UA).

70 The UA process was carried out using an ATOLab+ (3DLab Ltd.) system. A schematic of the UA process
71 is shown in Supplementary Material Figure S2. The chamber was evacuated till the O content in the
72 chamber was about 10 ppm, then filled with Ar (99.998 % purity). A crucible with steel inset was used.
73 The machine was operated at a vibration frequency of 35 kHz, an amplitude of 60 % and an arc current
74 of 100 A (at arc light up) up to 165 A. The entire atomization process was carried out under continuously
75 flowing Ar atmosphere (99.998 % purity) with a flow rate of 25 l/min. The rods were systematically fed
76 into the atomization chamber; a small part of the rod was then melted by an electric arc and deposited
77 on the steel inset. The deposited material is maintained in a molten state using the movable arc. Further,
78 the ultrasonic vibration is transferred from the cold end of the sonotrode towards the hot end, which
79 forms capillary waves on the surface of the molten pool. Once the critical vibration amplitude is reached,
80 the droplets were ejected to the flowing Ar stream, which cools them instantly and carried them to the
81 cyclone chamber. Further details of the ATO machine can be found in Ref. [37]. The powders were
82 collected in a sealed chamber and transferred to a glove box all under Ar atmosphere.

83 To heat treat the atomized powder, a Mo foil envelope was created, the powder was then placed inside
84 this Mo envelope. This powder-containing Mo envelope was then heat-treated at 1100 °C for 1 h in an
85 HTRT 70-600/18 resistance tube furnace (Carbolite Gero GmbH & Co. KG, Germany), employing three
86 evacuation-backfilling cycles followed by continuous Ar flow (99.998 % purity) to minimize further
87 oxidation. Atomized powder was also consolidated via FAST at 1100
88 and 1130 °C with a force of 24 kN and for a dwell time of 5 min.

2.2 Compositional analysis

89 The composition of the drop cast rods, atomized and heat-treated powder as well as the FAST sample
90 were obtained using inductively coupled plasma optical emission spectrometry (ICP-OES) for Fe, Cr,

91 Ti, and Y. Similarly, carrier gas hot extraction (CGHE) was used to analyze O and N concentration.
92 Furthermore, the O and N concentration of raw materials were measured using CGHE. At least five
93 measurements were recorded for each condition to produce reasonable statistical data.

2.3. Microstructural characterization

94 The microstructural characterization of the alloy was carried out at distinct stages of the process. For
95 scanning electron microscopy (SEM) investigation of the drop cast rod (cross-section view), the rods
96 were sectioned using a diamond wire saw, ground with SiC abrasive sheets up to P4000 followed by
97 polishing using 3 and 1 μm diamond suspension (5 min) and Buehler ITW (Germany) colloidal silica
98 (10 min) on semiautomatic LaboPol-60 machine (Struers, Germany). The final polishing was carried
99 out in a Vibromet machine (Buehler ITW, Germany) using a non-crystallizing oxide suspension
100 (Struers, Germany) for 10 h.

101 The powders were first cold embedded mounted in a resin to obtain the cross-section specimen of the
102 atomized and heat-treated powder (Epoclear, Schmitz-Metallographie GmbH, Germany). Once cured,
103 the pellets were further hot embedded in EpoMet F (Buehler ITW, Germany). In the case of the
104 consolidated sample, the specimens were cut using a diamond wire saw to obtain cross-sections. These
105 pieces were then hot embedded like the powder samples. The final specimen preparation was carried
106 out following the metallographic procedures analogous to those employed for the rods. Furthermore, the
107 specimens for the top-view of powder were prepared by simply adhering the powder on a carbon tape.

108 Secondary electron (SEM-SE) and backscattered electron (SEM-BSE) contrast micrographs were
109 obtained at an acceleration voltage of 20 kV using a Zeiss LEO 1530 scanning electron microscope
110 (SEM, by Zeiss, Germany). Additionally, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (SEM-EDS) of the rods,
111 powder and consolidated specimens were obtained using a Zeiss Auriga 60 system operating at 20 kV
112 with Octane Super-A detector (Ametek, USA).

113 Specimens for X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis were prepared by mounting powder on a stub with
114 resin, dried adequately, and polished to ensure a flat surface. The samples were then analyzed using a
115 D2 Phaser device (Bruker Corp.) equipped with a Cu $K\alpha$ source and a 1D LynxEye line detector. The
116 XRD measurement was carried out over a span of 10 to 145° at a step size of 0.01° and the operating
117 voltage and current of the source were kept at 30 kV and 10 mA. The accumulated acquisition time was
118 384 s per step.

119 Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) sample preparation was done with a Helios G4 focused ion
120 beam (FIB)-SEM system by (ThermoFisher, USA). TEM investigations were conducted on a Tecnai
121 F20 G2 SuperTwin microscope (ThermoFisher, USA) operated with a nominal acceleration voltage of
122 200 kV. High angle annular dark field images (HAADF) were obtained with a Fischione detector of
123 type M3000 (E.A. Fischione Instruments, Inc., USA). Energy dispersive X-ray (STEM-EDS) spectra
124 were acquired with an EDAX detector of type Elite T Super with a sensor area of 70 mm^2 (Ametek,
125 USA).

126 Atom probe tomography (APT) specimens were prepared directly from the powder samples using the
127 conventional lift-out method in a FIB-SEM Strata 400S (ThermoFisher, USA). The APT measurements
128 were conducted using a LEAP 4000X HR instrument (Cameca SAS) equipped with a UV laser operating
129 at a wavelength of 355 nm. The experimental parameters were set to a specimen temperature of 50 K, a
130 laser pulse energy of 50 pJ, a pulse frequency of 200 kHz, and a target detection rate between 0.3% and
131 1%. Three-dimensional reconstruction of the data was carried out with IVAS software version 3.6.14
132 (Cameca SAS), using SEM micrographs for guidance.

2.4 Microhardness tests

133 To evaluate the local mechanical properties of the alloys after sintering, microhardness measurements
134 were performed on the FAST sample using a Qness Q10+ microhardness tester with a load of HV0.05.
135 For each specific region, the hardness was determined by averaging the results of 20 individual indents.

3. Results

3.1 Impurity concentration of raw materials

136 Since the formation of oxide particles via internal oxidation is being investigated in this study, it is of
137 paramount importance that the impurity content in the alloys is tracked throughout the entire processing
138 route, beginning with the raw materials. The O and N concentration of the raw materials are given in
139 Table 1.

Table 1: O and N content in the raw materials via CGHE.

Raw materials	O / wt.%	N / wt.%
Fe	0.0136 ± 0.0011	0.0003 ± 0.0010
Cr	0.0118 ± 0.0020	0.0003 ± 0.0001
Ti	0.0181 ± 0.0016	0.0022 ± 0.0002
Y	0.8230 ± 0.0420	0.0070 ± 0.0010

140 It can be seen from Table 1 that the O content in Fe, Cr and Ti used is low (<0.02 wt.%), while the
141 elemental Y used in the study has a significantly higher concentration of O (0.823 wt.%). N
142 contamination is generally found to be negligible.

3.2 As-cast condition

143 To atomize the powders in the UA device, rods were drop-cast (Supplementary Material Figure S2). To
144 get a significant amount of powder at the end of the atomization process, four identically sized rods were
145 drop-cast. A schematic of the drop cast rods is shown in Figure 1a. The microstructure and composition
146 were carefully investigated for both ends (top and bottom) of each of the four rods to ensure
147 compositional homogeneity prior to UA. This is crucial because there is a chance of elements with
148 different densities (Fe: 7.87 g/cm³, Cr: 7.19 g/cm³, Y: 4.47 g/cm³ and Ti: 4.54 g/cm³ [38]) to separate
149 during drop casting under the influence of gravity. This could cause compositional inhomogeneity in
150 the rods which could be then carried over in the atomized powder.

Figure 1: a) Schematic of the drop cast rod along with SEM-BSE micrograph of the top and bottom section of the drop-cast rod showing a dendritic microstructure. b) SEM-EDS maps showing uniform distribution of Fe, Cr, Ti, O, and Y at a representative section of the microstructure showing a concentration of Y in the interdendritic regions and c) SEM-EBSD Kikuchi pattern of the Y-enriched phase in the interdendritic regions indicating the crystal structure of Fe₁₀Cr₂Y (ThMn₁₂ prototype, space group no. 139).

151 The representative microstructure of the top and bottom section of one rod is also shown in Figure 1a.
 152 SEM-BSE micrographs acquired from both sections of the rod reveal a microstructure characteristic of
 153 dendritic solidification. The microstructure is composed of a matrix with large grains that exhibits a
 154 darker contrast. A bright phase appears in interdendritic regions, both along the matrix grain boundaries
 155 and within the matrix grain interiors. The brighter contrast suggests an enrichment in elements with
 156 relatively high atomic number. As shown in the SEM-EDS elemental distribution map in Figure 1b,
 157 these regions are indeed enriched in Y, while Fe, Cr, and Ti are uniformly distributed across the
 158 microstructure. The dendrites, in contrast, are depleted in Y but maintain a relatively uniform
 159 distribution of Fe, Cr, and Ti. The homogeneous presence of O further eliminates the possibility that the
 160 phase in the interdendritic regions is an oxide. The chemical compositions of Y-poor, dendrites and the
 161 Y-rich phase in the interdendritic regions, determined by standard-free SEM-EDS, are summarized in
 162 Table 2. Based on these observations, an intermetallic phase with an Fe:Cr:Y atomic ratio of
 163 approximately 80:13:7 in the interdendritic regions is confirmed.

164 The crystal structures were investigated by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis performed on the rod
 165 samples. The XRD patterns confirmed the formation of the body-centered cubic (BCC) solid solution
 166 (W prototype, space group no. 229) corresponding to the matrix. The respective diffraction patterns are
 167 provided in Supplementary Material Figure S3. The volume fraction of the Y-enriched intermetallic
 168 phase appears too small to be detected by XRD. To further identify the structure of the intermetallic
 169 phase, SEM-EBSD analyses were conducted in the Y-rich interdendritic regions. The corresponding
 170 Kikuchi diffraction pattern and its indexed solution are shown in Figure 1c. The indexing result indicates
 171 a crystal structure like in Fe₁₀Cr₂Y (ThMn₁₂ prototype, space group no. 139).

172 The presence of a dendritic microstructure in the cast rods is not particularly concerning for the intended
 173 processing scheme, as the rods undergo remelting during the atomization process, wherein Y is fully
 174 miscible with both Fe and Cr in the liquid state. More importantly, the microstructure being consistent
 175 in the top and bottom sections of each rod indicates a high degree of chemical homogeneity. To further

176 substantiate this observation, chemical analyses of samples collected from the top and bottom portions
 177 of all four rods are presented in Table 2.

178 It can be seen from Table 2 that the overall alloy composition is close to the desired composition of Fe-
 179 14Cr-0.4Ti-0.5Y in wt.%. The maximum deviation from the desired composition is observed for Fe
 180 (~2 wt.%), relatively small deviations are observed for Cr (0.2 wt.%) and Y (0.03 wt.%) while almost
 181 no deviation can be observed for Ti. The O concentration from the top and bottom of all four rods seems
 182 to be rather uniform ranging between 0.005-0.020 wt.%. This slight variation can be expected since the
 183 four rods were cast in different casting experiments. Notably, the N concentration is low at this stage
 184 with the highest amount being 0.002 wt.%. Comparing these values to the alloys produced by MA is not
 185 trivial, since these alloys are produced using Y₂O₃ powders. Not many studies report accurate O/N
 186 contents measured via CGHE and if so, they usually do not distinguish the measured O content into O
 187 from the Y₂O₃ powders and excess O picked up during the process. However, García-
 188 Rodríguez et al. [39] reported the excess O content (obtained by removing the O content equivalent to
 189 the Y₂O₃ from the total measured O content: the Fe-14Cr-5Al-3W ODS alloy contained 0.297 wt.%
 190 excess O and 0.220 wt.% N, while the Fe-20Cr-5Al-3W alloy had lower levels of 0.104 wt.% O and
 191 0.033 wt.% N. A comparison of these values clearly indicates that impurity uptake, at least during the
 192 arc melting stage, is significantly lower than that observed in the mechanical alloying process.

Table 2: Chemical composition obtained by ICP-OES and CGHE from the top and the bottom of four rods after arc melting and drop casting. The desired composition is also added for comparison. The composition of the matrix and intermetallic dendritic arms (observed in Figure 1a) obtained by SEM-EDS is also included.

Specimen condition		Average composition / wt.%					
		Fe	Cr	Ti	Y	O	N
Desired		85.1	14	0.4	0.5	–	–
Rod 1	Top	84.1 ± 1.0	13.6 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.002	0.45 ± 0.01	0.004 ± 0.002	<0.0005
	Bottom	84.3 ± 0.8	13.8 ± 0.3	0.40 ± 0.002	0.48 ± 0.01	0.005 ± 0.001	<0.0005
Rod 2	Top	83.0 ± 0.1	13.9 ± 0.1	0.41 ± 0.004	0.45 ± 0.02	0.022 ± 0.002	0.002 ± 0.0007
	Bottom	82.7 ± 0.1	13.8 ± 0.1	0.40 ± 0.004	0.41 ± 0.02	0.007 ± 0.001	<0.001
Rod 3	Top	82.8 ± 0.2	13.9 ± 0.1	0.40 ± 0.002	0.44 ± 0.02	0.015 ± 0.001	0.002 ± 0.0003
	Bottom	82.7 ± 0.4	13.8 ± 0.1	0.43 ± 0.005	0.51 ± 0.09	0.005 ± 0.003	<0.001
Rod 4	Top	82.4 ± 0.1	13.8 ± 0.1	0.40 ± 0.001	0.53 ± 0.01	0.013 ± 0.001	<0.001
	Bottom	82.6 ± 0.3	13.9 ± 0.1	0.40 ± 0.001	0.49 ± 0.01	0.005 ± 0.001	<0.001
Avg.		83.1 ± 0.6	13.8 ± 0.1	0.39 ± 0.02	0.47 ± 0.02	0.009 ± 0.003	<0.001
Dendrites (SEM-EDS)		85.2 ± 0.5	14.2 ± 0.1	0.36 ± 0.03	0 ± 0.10	–	–
Interdendritic regions (SEM-EDS)		80.9 ± 0.5	12.1 ± 0.1	0.42 ± 0.04	6.56 ± 0.10	–	–

3.3 Ultrasonic atomized and heat-treated powders

193 In this section, the morphology, microstructure and chemical composition of the powder samples
194 produced by UA are presented. The results are categorized into two distinct powder conditions: the as-
195 atomized state (AA), representing powder collected directly from the atomization process, and the heat-
196 treated state (HT), referring to powder subjected to annealing at 1100 °C for 1 h. The heat treatment was
197 performed to investigate one of two possible scenarios. In the first scenario, the heat treatment may
198 facilitate nucleation and growth if the oxide dispersoids are not formed during atomization. In the second
199 scenario, the heat treatment enables examination of possible changes in composition and size if such
200 dispersoids are already present after atomization.

201 Figure 2a presents the top-view SEM-SE micrographs of the AA powder. The powder particles exhibit
202 a predominantly spherical morphology with an average diameter of $(59 \pm 10) \mu\text{m}$ and a high sphericity
203 of (0.90 ± 0.07) . To investigate the microstructure of the powder particles, cross-sectional SEM-BSE
204 micrographs were obtained, as shown in Figures 2b–c. Two notable observations can be made: (i) The
205 powder particles are dense and nearly pore-free. This is a clear advantage over gas atomization processes
206 where hollow powder particles are common [40,41]. (ii) More importantly, the powder particles as
207 shown for example in Figures 2b–c contain uniformly distributed dispersoids which appear as spots or
208 specks throughout the SEM-BSE micrographs. These dispersoids, ranging from approximately 20-
209 100 nm, are located both along grain boundaries and within the grain interior of the matrix. There are
210 two types of dispersoids with respect to contrast – dark and bright, marked with yellow and blue arrows
211 in Figure 1c, respectively. The lower BSE contrast of the dispersoids suggests that they contain lighter
212 elements, indicating a possible formation of an oxide or nitride phase. Based on the microstructural
213 observations of the rods in Figure 1, the bright phase is inferred to have a higher concentration of Y
214 compared to the surrounding matrix and could potentially be a Y-rich intermetallic phase.

215 Figure 2d presents the top-view SEM-SE micrographs of the HT powder particles. The particles appear
216 partially agglomerated, which can be attributed to diffusion bonding occurring between adjacent
217 particles during the heat treatment process. Figures 2e–f display the microstructure of an individual HT
218 powder particle. It is evident from these images that the type of dispersoids (dark and bright) observed
219 in the AA condition are also present in the HT state, indicating a high degree of thermal stability of these
220 dispersoids. The two types of dispersoids are marked in Figure 2f with yellow (dark specks) and blue
221 (bright specks) arrows like in Figure 2c.

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of: (a-c) AA powder and (d-f) HT powder. (a,c) top view SE images, (b,e) BSE cross-section images, and (c,f) their magnified regions. The yellow and blue arrows highlight the dark and bright contrast dispersoids.

222 The dispersoids are, however, distributed non-uniformly across the powder particles in terms of their
 223 number, size, and spatial distribution. To categorize the powder particles, they are classified into three
 224 groups based on the dispersoid density within a given micrograph area as shown in Table 3. For
 225 statistical consistency, cross-section SEM-BSE images of 100 AA powder particles were analyzed at
 226 identical magnification (20,000 x) with an imaged area of $130 \mu\text{m}^2$. The same reference area is used for
 227 the analysis of all SEM-BSE micrographs. The mean dispersoid radius, number of dispersoids, and
 228 volume fraction were calculated using ImageJ software. Based on the number density of dispersoids,
 229 the powder particles are grouped as follows: low density with $< 40 \cdot 100 \mu\text{m}^2$, medium density with
 230 $(40-200) \cdot 100 \mu\text{m}^2$, and high density with $> 200 \cdot 100 \mu\text{m}^2$. The dispersoid size was determined by
 231 considering at least 200 dispersoids for each of the three categories. The inter-dispersoid distance
 232 referred the distance between the center of two dispersoids which was calculated using the following
 233 relation [42]:

234

$$L = r \sqrt{\frac{32}{3\pi f}} \quad (1)$$

235 Where L is the center-to-center interparticle distance, r is the mean radius of the dispersoids, and f is
 236 the volume fraction of the dispersoids. The reported error represents the deviation obtained after
 237 analyzing multiple images of the same reference area ($130 \mu\text{m}^2$).

Table 3: Quantitative classification of AA powder particles based on dispersoid density, showing the representative microstructures, average dispersoid size, inter-dispersoid spacing and dispersoid volume fraction for the low, medium, and high dispersoid density categories.

Dispersoid number density ($100 \mu\text{m}^{-2}$)			
	Low (< 40)	Medium (40-200)	High (> 200)
Inter-dispersoid distance (μm)	1.9 ± 0.7	0.9 ± 0.4	0.6 ± 0.3
Dispersoid size (nm)	100 ± 53	108 ± 65	101 ± 70
Dispersoid volume fraction (vol.%)	0.7 ± 0.2	4.2 ± 1.1	12.5 ± 2.4

238 Among the 100 analyzed powder particles, the majority exhibit medium dispersoid density (51 %),
 239 followed by low (38 %), and high dispersoid density particles forming the smallest fraction (10 %). The
 240 inter-dispersoid spacing is the largest for particles with low dispersoid density and the smallest for those
 241 with high density. This trend is expected, as the dispersoids are homogeneously distributed within each
 242 individual particle. Notably, the average dispersoid size remains nearly identical across all three
 243 categories, strongly implying an identical dispersoid formation mechanism in all powder particles.

244 The chemical composition (determined by ICP-OES) of the atomized and heat-treated powders are
 245 shown in Table 4. Most notably, a loss of around 0.2 wt.% of Y loss is recorded in the atomized powders
 246 with (0.30 ± 0.01) wt.% compared to drop cast rods with (0.47 ± 0.02) wt.%. The O content increased
 247 to (0.079 ± 0.001) wt.% which indicates some pickup of O during the atomization process despite the
 248 < 10 ppm level O maintained in the Ar atmosphere of the ATO device during atomization. However,
 249 this content is still lower than O picked up during the MA process of several 0.1 wt.% O as described in
 250 the previous section. Powders from the AA and HT condition still show a ferritic (BCC) matrix with no
 251 peaks corresponding to the dispersoid phase are observed. These XRD results are shown in the
 252 Supplementary Material Figure S3.

Table 4: Chemical composition of AA and HT powder conditions obtained by ICP-OES and CGHE. The nominal composition has also been added for comparison.

Specimen Condition	Average composition / wt.%					
	Fe	Cr	Ti	Y	O	N
Desired	85.1	14	0.4	0.5	-	-
AA	83.4 ± 0.2	13.2 ± 0.1	0.430 ± 0.004	0.290 ± 0.005	0.079 ± 0.001	0.003 ± 0.001
HT	84.7 ± 0.5	13.0 ± 0.1	0.410 ± 0.003	0.290 ± 0.002	0.102 ± 0.012	0.006 ± 0.001

253 To determine the chemical composition of the dispersoids, APT samples were prepared from powder
 254 particles for the AA and HT condition. To maintain consistency, all the lift-outs for APT were done
 255 from particles with a medium dispersoid number density. Two tips, each of the AA and HT condition,
 256 are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Reconstructed map of APT dataset containing elemental distribution maps, isosurface constructions and one-dimensional concentration profiles for dispersoids for: a,b) AA powder and c,d) HT powder.

257 Figures 3a–b illustrate the APT results obtained from the AA powder, showing the spatial distribution
 258 of six elements: Fe, Cr, Ti, Y, O, and N. While Fe, Cr, and Ti exhibit relatively uniform distribution,
 259 noticeable inhomogeneity is evident for N, O, and Y. To further examine these regions of compositional
 260 variation, isosurfaces were constructed at 4 at.% for Ti and 4 at.% for N, as displayed in the enlarged
 261 view of Figure 3a. For Figure 3b, an isosurface for 9 at.% Y was made, since no clear inhomogeneity
 262 was observed for Ti and N. Isosurfaces corresponding to a particular element delineate regions of high
 263 concentration of this particular element within the tip, revealing distinct interfaces between the element-
 264 rich regions and the surrounding matrix. These isosurfaces may represent either segregation, clusters or
 265 a secondary phase [43,44]. Segregation at grain boundaries, for example, generally spans a few nm with
 266 a spike in the concentration of one or a few elements. A cluster typically describes a small group of
 267 solute atoms detected as a local enrichment above the random matrix composition, often only a few

268 nanometers or less in size, as is the case for the Y-Ti-O nanoclusters widely reported in ODS steel
269 literature [10,19]. Secondary phases are, however, typically larger and often feature a sharp chemical
270 interface to the matrix.

271 To quantify the composition of these features, a cylindrical region of interest (ROI) traversing each
272 isosurface was defined, from which a one-dimensional (1D) concentration profile was extracted. Based
273 on the size and compositional differences between the matrix and dispersoid observed in the 1D
274 concentration profiles, the regions delineated by the isosurfaces can be confidently identified as
275 dispersoids of secondary phases and not nanoclusters. Accordingly, the regions contained within the
276 isosurfaces will hereafter be designated simply as dispersoids.

277 For the first tip (Figure 3a), the resulting isosurfaces reveal two distinct types of dispersoids which are
278 labeled as Dispersoids 1 and 2 in Figure 3a. Dispersoid 1 corresponds to the region identified from the
279 N isosurface. It should be noted that the Y isosurface encompassed both types of dispersoids, indicating
280 that Y is enriched in both phases. The chemical composition of each dispersoid as well as of the matrix
281 is listed in Table 5. Dispersoid 1 is enriched primarily in Y (~62 at.%), N (~20 at.%), Fe (11 at.%) with
282 some traces of O and Ti. This composition indicates the presence of a complex Y-oxynitride.
283 Dispersoid 2, however, is significantly different from Dispersoid 1. The 1D concentration profile of
284 Dispersoid 2 reveals a Y-Ti-O oxide with Y (~42 at.%), O (~45 at.%) and Ti (~10 at.%). It is completely
285 depleted in Fe, Cr and N. For the second tip (Figure 3b), Dispersoid 3 is not enriched in O or N and
286 exhibits a composition that is close to an intermetallic phase with approximately Fe (~80 at.%), Cr
287 (~6 at.%), and Y (~12 at.%). Notably, this composition is very similar to that of the intermetallic phase
288 observed within the interdendritic regions of the as-cast microstructure, see Table 3.

289 To determine the crystal structure of the dispersoids, transmission electron microscopy (TEM) analyses
290 were carried out on one AA powder particle with a medium dispersoid density like the one for APT.
291 The results are shown in Figure S5 of the Supplementary Material. It can be clearly seen that the
292 dispersoid captured in TEM is an intermetallic phase with a crystal structure of ThMn₁₂ prototype (space
293 group no. 139), exactly like the intermetallic phase observed in the as-cast microstructure (Figure 1).

294 It is likewise essential to determine the composition of the dispersoids for the HT condition. This
295 approach enables determining whether their composition differs from those seen in the AA condition.
296 Figures 3c–d presents the APT results obtained from two tips of the HT powder. Fe, Cr, and Ti exhibit
297 uniform distributions, whereas O and Y display evident inhomogeneity in both tips. In contrast to the
298 AA tips, however, no inhomogeneity associated with N is observed in the HT tips. Two different
299 isosurfaces were utilized here, i.e. 2 at.% Y (Figure 3c) and 4 at.% Ti (Figure 3d). 1D concentration
300 profiles were extracted along cylindrical ROIs for the selected dispersoids, labeled Dispersoids 4
301 (Figure 3c) and 5, 6 (Figure 3d), consistent with the methodology used in Figures 3a–b. All three
302 dispersoids exhibit nearly identical compositions, consisting of approximately Y (~42 at.%),
303 O (~45 at.%), and Ti (~10 at.%). This composition closely resembles that of the oxide dispersoid
304 identified in the AA condition. It must be noted that the concentrations of unmarked dispersoids were
305 also studied, and their compositions are identical to the marked ones. Considering the composition of
306 the oxide dispersoids in both the AA and HT conditions are very similar, these dispersoids are hence
307 forth named as Y₄₂Ti₁₀O₄₅.

Table 5: Chemical composition of dispersoids (in at.%) marked 1-6 in Figure 3 and their surrounding matrix.

		Fe	Cr	Ti	Y	O	N
Tip 1 (Figure 3a)	Disp. 1	11.6 ± 1.1	0.9 ± 0.1	0.05 ± 0.02	62.7 ± 3.4	3.3 ± 0.9	20.4 ± 2.1
	Disp. 2	1.5 ± 0.9	0.02 ± 0.01	9.7 ± 1.2	41.9 ± 2.3	45.2 ± 1.9	0.04 ± 0.02
	Matrix	83.5 ± 3.2	14.9 ± 2.1	1.3 ± 0.5	0.09 ± 0.01	0.2 ± 0.1	0
Tip 2 (Figure 3b)	Disp.3	80.2 ± 3.3	6.34 ± 1.2	1.4 ± 0.5	11.6 ± 2.1	0.1 ± 0.1	0
	Matrix	84.1 ± 2.8	13.3 ± 1.9	1.3 ± 0.42	0.010 ± 0.001	0.2 ± 0.1	0
Tip 3 (Figure 3c)	Disp.4	3.8 ± 0.8	0.8 ± 0.1	9.2 ± 1.3	41.5 ± 2.5	44.3 ± 4.1	0.01 ± 0.01
	Matrix	84.8 ± 2.4	14.7 ± 1.6	0.4 ± 0.19	0.050 ± 0.002	0.2 ± 0.1	0
Tip 4 (Figure 3d)	Disp.5	0.5 ± 0.1	0.8 ± 0.2	9.6 ± 1.7	41.9 ± 3.1	46.9 ± 2.1	0.02 ± 0.01
	Disp.6	2.2 ± 1.2	0.7 ± 0.1	10.4 ± 1.6	41.4 ± 3.2	44.9 ± 3.1	0.02 ± 0.01
	Matrix	84.9 ± 2.1	14.1 ± 1.3	0.4 ± 0.1	0.010 ± 0.01	0.3 ± 0.1	0

308 Although only two tips per powder condition are shown here, multiple APT runs were carried out to
309 capture dispersoids within the tips. Of the seven successful AA tips, only two contained dispersoids,
310 whereas both successful HT tips revealed dispersoids. The absence of dispersoids in the remaining AA
311 tips can be explained by the inter-dispersoid distance reported in Table 4. For a medium dispersoid
312 number density (where the lift-out was made), the mean inter-dispersoid spacing was $(0.9 \pm 0.4) \mu\text{m}$,
313 which, relative to the tip size of a few hundred nm, indicates that the analyzed volume simply did not
314 intersect a dispersoid.

315 Supplementary Material Table S1 presents the Y distribution in all successfully reconstructed tips from
316 both the AA and HT conditions, along with the corresponding bulk elemental compositions obtained
317 across all analyzed tips. It is noteworthy that in tips lacking dispersoids, the Y content is nearly zero.
318 This clearly indicates that the available Y in all powder particles is almost entirely consumed in the
319 formation of dispersoids, leaving negligible Y dissolved in the matrix.

3.4 Consolidated material

320 To produce solid bulk samples, AA powder was consolidated using FAST to obtain a bulk pellet with a
321 diameter of 20 mm and a height of 10 mm. Initial consolidation was carried out at 1100 °C to maintain
322 consistency with the HT samples. However, FAST-processed pellets at this temperature were
323 incompletely sintered, exhibiting large cavities and significant porosity of about $(3.2 \pm 0.9) \text{ vol.}\%$
324 mostly along the sinter joints. Consequently, the processing temperature was slightly increased to
325 1130 °C. At this higher temperature, a dense and well-consolidated sample was achieved with a porosity
326 of $(0.7 \pm 0.2) \text{ vol.}\%$. Therefore, all subsequent discussions of the FAST samples refer to specimens
327 sintered at 1130 °C. SEM-BSE microstructures corresponding to two identical regions in the FAST
328 sample consolidated at 1130 °C is shown in Figures 5a–b. The chemical composition of the FAST
329 sample is provided in Table 6.

Table 6: Chemical composition of FAST sample obtained by ICP-OES and CGHE. The nominal composition has also been added for comparison.

Specimen Condition	Average composition / wt.%					
	Fe	Cr	Ti	Y	O	N
Desired	85.1	14	0.4	0.5	-	-
FAST	83.2 ± 0.3	13.2 ± 0.1	0.42 ± 0.01	0.29 ± 0.01	0.09 ± 0.01	0.003 ± 0.001

330 The individual powder particles making up the FAST sample remain distinguishable due to the visible
 331 sinter boundaries. Like in the AA powder, the spatial distribution of the dispersoids (observed as dark
 332 specks) is notably non-uniform. Classification of different regions based on dispersoid number density
 333 measured in micrographs of a uniform reference area (130 μm²), is feasible owing to the pronounced
 334 spatial heterogeneity of dispersoid distribution. Regions within the FAST sample can again be
 335 categorized into regions of low, medium, and high dispersoid number density as used in Table 3. For
 336 enhanced visualization, two representative regions from each category were selected and their
 337 microstructures magnified.

Figure 4: SEM-BSE micrographs obtained in the FAST sample: (a,b) powder particles. Enlarged particles containing (c,d) low, (e,f) high and (g,h) medium dispersoid number density.

338 To establish a correlation between the observed dispersoid number density and the local Y concentration
 339 within the respective particles, SEM-EDS analyses were performed in regions corresponding to high,

340 medium, and low dispersoid number density. The resulting data are summarized in Table 7. From these
 341 measurements, a clear relationship emerges: particles exhibiting a high dispersoid density also possess
 342 an elevated Y content (2.46 wt.%). In contrast, Y was not detected in particles with low dispersoid
 343 density, while particles with medium dispersoid densities display intermediate Y concentrations, as
 344 expected.

Table 7: Composition of individual powder particles in the FAST specimen using SEM-EDS.

Dispersoid number density	Average Composition / wt.%			
	Fe	Cr	Ti	Y
Low	85.4 ± 0.3	14.29 ± 0.1	0.3 ± 0.1	0
Medium	85.2 ± 0.3	13.92 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1	0.4 ± 0.1
High	83.8 ± 0.3	13.04 ± 0.1	0.7 ± 0.1	2.5 ± 0.1

3.5 Microhardness testing

345 Given that ODS alloys are primarily designed for structural applications, it is crucial to evaluate their
 346 mechanical properties. Due to the heterogeneous distribution of dispersoids in the present alloy, Vickers
 347 microhardness tests were performed on the consolidated FAST sample. The FAST sample was selected
 348 instead of individual powder particles because hardness measurements on powder embedded in resin
 349 could yield unreliable results, as the resin's lower stiffness may influence the readings. In contrast, the
 350 compacted FAST sample provides a stable surface, enabling accurate and reproducible microhardness
 351 evaluation. Twenty indents were made in each of the low-, medium-, and high-dispersoid number
 352 density regions. The hardness values along with the average grain size of the matrix and the
 353 corresponding indent are compiled in Table 8. An increase in dispersoid number density results in
 354 evident grain refinement and a corresponding enhancement in hardness.

Table 8: Vickers micro-hardness test results and the average matrix grain size of the low, medium and high dispersoid density regions of the FAST sample along with a representative indent of each region.

Dispersoid number density (100 μm⁻²)			
	Low (< 40)	Medium (40-200)	High (> 240)
Average grain size (μm)	17.4 ± 4.1	8.0 ± 2.3	2.4 ± 1.5
Hardness (HV0.05)	159 ± 7	190 ± 9	282 ± 18

4. Discussion

355 Y-enriched intermetallic phases (enrichment with respect to the surrounding matrix) were observed in
 356 the interdendritic regions of cast microstructures as well as in the form of dispersoids in the AA powder.
 357 In both cases, a ThMn₁₂ prototype phase was identified via SEM-EBSD (as-cast samples) and TEM (AA
 358 powder). This ThMn₁₂ prototype phase has been reported for the Fe-Ti-Y and Fe-Cr-Y ternary alloy

359 systems as the τ phase with a composition of $\text{Fe}_{12-x}\text{Ti}_x\text{Y}$ and $\text{Fe}_{12-x}\text{Cr}_x\text{Y}$, respectively. The most common
 360 phases reported are $\text{Fe}_{10.8}\text{Ti}_{1.2}\text{Y}$ [45], Fe_{11}TiY [46], $\text{Fe}_{10}\text{Cr}_2\text{Y}$ [47] and $\text{Fe}_{10.5}\text{Cr}_{1.5}\text{Y}$ [48]. This indicates a
 361 wide stability range of ThMn_{12} prototype phases. Although the composition of the intermetallic phase
 362 reported in Table 2 does not exactly match the ideal $\text{Fe}_{10}\text{Cr}_2\text{Y}$ stoichiometry, it is nonetheless closely
 363 aligned. The minor deviations observed may be attributed to experimental uncertainties like the
 364 difference between the large probe size and small phase size (SEM-EDS/STEM-EDS) and low detection
 365 efficiencies (APT).

366 To examine how the elemental concentration of O and Y, change throughout the different processing
 367 stages (arc melting, as-atomized, heat-treated, and FAST), the corresponding concentrations of Y and O
 368 (in wt.%) are presented for every processing stage in Figure 5. The concentrations of Fe, Cr and Ti do
 369 not change significantly across the entire processing route (Table 3–5). Therefore, only the elements
 370 mainly relevant for the dispersoid formation (Y and O) are plotted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Evolution of chemical concentrations through the processing route for (a) O and (b) Y.

371 The observed decrease in Y content from 0.46 wt.% after arc melting to 0.29 wt.% following atomization
 372 is unlikely due to evaporation during the atomization process. If evaporation were responsible, a similar
 373 loss would be expected during the initial arc melting and drop casting, which is not observed since the
 374 arc melted samples maintain a Y content close to the intended 0.5 wt.%. Given that the melting points
 375 of Fe (1538 °C), Cr (1860 °C), Ti (1670 °C) and Y (1526 °C) are also quite similar to each other [38],
 376 selective evaporation of Y is unlikely. Instead, the loss in Y is most likely caused by the inhomogeneous
 377 distribution of Y across the powder particles and the left-over material in the atomization chamber
 378 (material that was not atomized and cooled down slowly). This is verified by data in Figure S4 and
 379 Table S2 in the Supplementary Material. The microstructure of the left-over materials closely resembles
 380 those observed in the drop cast rods (Figure 1). However, the overall Y concentration in the left-over
 381 material of (2.3 ± 1.7) wt.% is considerably higher than the nominal composition of 0.5 wt.%. Thus, the
 382 reduction of the Y concentration from 0.46 wt.% to 0.29 wt.% can be attributed to the loss of Y to the
 383 left-over material, not being atomized in the process.

384 During subsequent heat treatment and FAST, the Y content remains relatively stable, suggesting that
 385 the major shift in Y concentration happens primarily at the atomization stage due to Y heterogeneity in
 386 the powder rather than any evaporation. The O content shows an opposite trend compared to Y during
 387 processing. O increases significantly from 0.009 wt.% after arc melting to 0.079 wt.% after atomization.
 388 It remains relatively stable during the heat treatment and field-assisted sintering technique steps. This O

389 uptake during atomization is proven to be critical for the formation of the oxide dispersoids in this step
390 by the present work confirming the formation of oxide particles right during the atomization step.

391 Using the ICP-OES average Y concentration of 0.29 wt.% in the atomized powder and assuming all Y
392 is consumed to form $Y_{42}Ti_{10}O_{45}$ dispersoids, the O required for this stoichiometry would be about
393 0.057 wt.%. Since the measured O content in the atomized sample is 0.079 wt.%, Y may be the limiting
394 factor for dispersoid formation. However, this calculation is based on averaged O and Y contents after
395 atomization. As discussed above, the actual local concentrations vary between individual powder
396 particles depending on their Y content. Such heterogeneity with respect to O and Y availability and
397 distribution will influence the dispersoid formation process on a particle-by-particle basis. This nuanced
398 understanding is important for interpreting the formation of oxide dispersoids during internal oxidation.

399 The Y-Ti-O-type nanocluster dispersoids generally reported in literature are Y_2TiO_5 and $Y_2Ti_2O_7$ [5,6].
400 Besides these, there are also certain other types of oxide nanoclusters with compositions around
401 $Ti_{35}Y_{17}O_{40}$ as reported by Schneibel et al. [19]. The $Y_{42}Ti_{10}O_{45}$ oxide dispersoids (Fig 3a-b) obtained in
402 the AA and HT condition are however of a seemingly different composition, especially with respect to
403 the Y-to-Ti ratio. The experimentally obtained ratio from the present work has never been reported in
404 literature before. This new dispersoid type might be a new stable or metastable oxide that forms under
405 the non-equilibrium conditions of the UA process. The presence of $Y_{42}Ti_{10}O_{45}$ dispersoids in the AA
406 and HT condition, together with the complete depletion of Y in the matrix under these conditions (as
407 shown in Figure 3 and Supplementary Material Table S1), suggests that nearly all dispersoids are formed
408 during the UA process. The absence of matrix Y consequently precludes any further nucleation or
409 growth of dispersoids during subsequent thermal treatments (HT or FAST).

410 It must be noted that a complex oxynitride was also observed in the APT tips of the AA condition
411 (Figure 3a-b). This indicates that not only oxides but also nitrides can form during UA. However, since
412 the ratio of O:N is ~ 26 for the AA powders and ~ 17 for the HT powders (Table 4), the number density
413 of nitrides can be expected to be at least one order of magnitude lower than that of the oxides. However,
414 the number of intermetallic dispersoids compared to that of oxides is not easy to predict.

415 There are in principle only two routes for the dispersoids to form via nucleation and growth during the
416 atomization process:

- 417 1. Primary solidification of the dispersoids from the liquid phase before the matrix and
- 418 2. Precipitation from the solid phase during cooling after solidification of the powder particles

419 To determine which of these mechanisms is likely active, we first examine the spatial distribution of the
420 dispersoids. Precipitation of the oxides from the solid phase would be expected to proceed via
421 heterogeneous nucleation at the grain boundaries of the solidified powder particle. However, since the
422 micrographs shown in Figure 2 clearly show a uniform distribution of dispersoids with no preference
423 over grain boundaries, this is the first indication that the formation of the dispersoids does proceed via
424 primary solidification from the liquid.

425 The second evidence for the formation of dispersoids via primary solidification is the variance in size
426 of the dispersoids. The average size of the dispersoids is ~ 100 nm. For an oxide nucleus to grow to 100
427 nm, the diffusivity of Y in the matrix (either solid or liquid) must be fast enough to enable diffusion
428 length of at least 100 nm. Whether dispersoids originate in the solid or liquid phase can be assessed by
429 comparing the diffusion distances that Y atoms must cover under each condition to achieve a particle
430 size of about 100 nm.

431 It must be noted that the cooling rate in the atomization process is extremely high. Notably, liquid
432 droplets are immediately cooled by the flowing Ar stream (Supplementary Material Figure S2) as soon
433 as they are detached from the melt pool due to capillary waves and suspended into the atomization
434 chamber. While data on exact values of cooling rates are not yet reported in literature, cooling rates from
435 gas atomization (10^6 K/s [49]) might be a good estimate also for the ATO system. For the following
436 calculation, a few reasonable assumptions are made:

- 437 1. The solidus temperature of the alloy is assumed to be similar to that of Fe-14Cr, which is
438 approximately 1535 °C (1808 K) according to the Fe-Cr phase diagram [50].
- 439 2. The diffusivity of Y in the molten alloy at 2410 °C is assumed to be comparable to that of Fe in
440 molten Fe at the same temperature, with an estimated value of about $9 \cdot 10^{-8}$ m²/s [51]. This
441 assumption is made because diffusivity data for Y in molten Fe-Cr alloys are not available in
442 literature.
- 443 3. The diffusivity of Y in the solid alloy is approximated by the diffusivity of Y in BCC Fe at 1500 °C,
444 which is around 10^{-15} m²/s. This temperature is selected based on the assumption that solid-state
445 precipitation, if it occurs, initiates immediately after solidification and continues until the
446 temperature decreases by approximately 500 K [52].

447 Taking the above parameters, a diffusion length scale for the two mechanisms mentioned above can be
448 calculated. For both cases, growth taking place within a temperature drop of 500 K is considered. This
449 assumption along with the assumption of the cooling rate, yields a growth time of $5 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s. The diffusion
450 distance for precipitate growth can be calculated by the equation $x \approx 2\sqrt{Dt}$, where D is the diffusion
451 coefficient and t refers to the time. In the solid state, the diffusion distance is approximately 1.4 nm.
452 This reflects the extremely limited atomic mobility within solids over the available diffusion time. Given
453 such a short diffusion distance, the growth of dispersoids to sizes on the order of 100 nm is extremely
454 unlikely under these conditions. In contrast, the calculated diffusion distance in the liquid phase extends
455 into the micrometer range, approximately 13 μm, indicative of the significantly enhanced atomic
456 mobility and mass transport. This substantial difference in diffusion lengths clearly demonstrates that
457 nucleation and growth of dispersoids to larger sizes, such as 100 nm, can be readily achieved in the
458 liquid phase due to its higher diffusivity and more favorable kinetic conditions.

459 Based on the preceding arguments and considering that the melting point of the $Y_{42}Ti_{10}O_{45}$ oxide is
460 expected to be comparable to that of Y_2O_3 , being approximately 2400 °C [57], it is highly probable that
461 the oxide dispersoids will solidify prior to the solidification of the surrounding matrix.

462 While it is confirmed that the formation of oxide dispersoids through Y internal oxidation is
463 thermodynamically feasible, the reasons for the uneven particle size and distribution must be explored.
464 During the UA process, the alloy on top of the sonotrode is maintained in a molten state for
465 approximately 3-5 min while the atomization process is running. Though the material is continuously
466 heated with a moving electric arc, a local temperature drop is not completely avoidable. This might have
467 caused the lighter element, e.g. Y, to enrich towards the top of the melt pool under the influence of
468 convection diffusion and gravity, hence, leading to a variation in Y concentration between powder
469 atomized from the top and bottom regions of a single melt pool. This is also the reason why the left-over
470 material showed a much larger Y concentration (see Supplementary Material Table S2).

471 The hardness data presented in Table 8 reveal a distinct correlation between dispersoid density and
472 microhardness. Regions characterized by a higher dispersoid density exhibit increased microhardness
473 values. This enhancement can be attributed to the combined effects of a greater dispersoid density and
474 a finer grain structure within these areas, acting synergistically to impede dislocation motion [53,54]. In

475 contrast, regions with lower dispersoid density display reduced microhardness due to decreased
476 hinderance to dislocation motion owing to the lesser density of dispersoids and the presence of coarser
477 grains [55,56]. A detailed quantification of these two aspects is, however, difficult at present as the
478 uncertainties in microstructural parameters arising from the measurement principles and intrinsic
479 microstructural variation propagate to even higher uncertainties of the resulting strengthening
480 contributions [6].

481 Given that the present work introduces a novel synthesis route, it is essential to contextualize the
482 obtained hardness values by comparing them with those reported for ferritic ODS alloys in the literature.
483 In terms of alloy composition, atomization and consolidation conditions, as well as post-processing
484 treatments, a systematic comparison of hardness values remains challenging due to the substantial
485 variations reported over several decades of research on Fe-based ODS systems. Nevertheless,
486 meaningful comparisons can still be made with studies that employ similar consolidation routes to the
487 present work without any subsequent post-processing, hence differing only in the atomization method.

488 Franke et al. [57] reported Vickers hardness values ranging from 238 to 322 HV10 for Fe-9Cr ODS
489 steels, observing that hardness increased with milling duration. Similarly, Boulnat et al. [58] reported
490 values between 250 and 330 HV10 for Fe-14Cr-1W-0.3Y₂O₃, with a peak hardness of (332 ± 6) HV10
491 achieved in the most densified compacts. Under a lower load, the hardness further increased to
492 (377 ± 67) HV0.05. In general, hardness values decrease with increasing indentation load, a trend
493 frequently reported for ferritic alloys within the 200–400 HV range [59]. This behavior is also evident
494 in Ref. [58], where reducing the load from HV10 to HV0.05 resulted in higher hardness values. Hence,
495 the hardness values obtained in the present study are expected to be slightly lower than those reported
496 in literature, if the load would be maintained equivalent across all studies.

497 The strengthening effect of dispersoids in the present study is, however, evident when comparing the
498 hardness of regions with high and low dispersoid densities. The high-density regions exhibit a hardness
499 of (282 ± 18) HV0.05, whereas the low-density regions show only (159 ± 7) HV0.05. This relative
500 increase of 80 % is comparable to that observed in Eurofer97, where the presence of dispersoids raises
501 the hardness from ~235 HV0.1 (no dispersoids) to ~365 HV0.1 [60]. While studies commonly report
502 ultrafine-grained microstructures (10–50 nm) with dispersoid sizes in the range of 5-50 nm in samples
503 produced via the MA route [5,6,61], the current UA-processed alloy exhibits a larger, average grain size
504 of approximately 2 μm and coarser dispersoids with mean radius of (101 ± 70) nm (Table 3).

505 While volume fractions of dispersoids are not always explicitly reported in the cited studies on MA Fe-
506 Cr ODS alloys, the data available consistently indicate typical dispersoids volume fractions of around
507 0.2–0.3 vol.% for nanosized Y₂O₃ or Y-Ti-O nanoclusters quantified via TEM and APT [62–64]. In
508 contrast, high-dispersoid density regions of the UA powders exhibit a markedly higher dispersoid
509 volume fraction of up to (12.5 ± 2.4) vol.% (Table 3). This elevated volume fraction in the UA process
510 potentially compensates for the larger grain sizes, yielding hardness values comparable to literature
511 reports for the MA processing route. A similar correlation between dispersoid size, volume fraction, and
512 strengthening was also reported by Luptáková et al. [65] who found that 5 vol.% of coarser oxides of
513 sizes greater than 20 nm provides mechanical reinforcement comparable to that in traditional dispersions
514 containing less than 1 vol.% of ultrafine oxides in the size range of 2–5 nm.

515 Although the hardness of the high dispersoid density region is comparable to ferritic ODS alloys
516 produced via MA followed by sintering, the inhomogeneity of the dispersoid distribution needs to be
517 tackled. Strategies such as fine tuning of atomization parameter or introducing controlled deformation-
518 assisted consolidation could improve dispersoid uniformity [66,67]. As the present study primarily aims

519 to establish the thermodynamic and kinetic feasibility of the proposed method for producing ODS
520 powders, a detailed investigation of process parameter optimization and post-processing lies beyond its
521 current scope and will be addressed in future work.

522 5. Conclusions

523 The Fe-14Cr-0.5Ti-0.5Y ferritic ODS alloy is manufactured via powder metallurgy route using a novel
524 ultrasonic atomization (UA) technique with elemental Y rather than Y_2O_3 . The formation mechanism of
525 dispersoids and their distribution in the powders are investigated. Based on experimental observations,
526 the following conclusions can be made.

- 527 • Using the UA technique, Y-Ti-O nanoclusters do not form. However, the present technique is
528 still successful in producing Y-Ti-O dispersoids in the range of 20–100 nm in the atomized
529 powder. In addition to the oxides, nitrides and intermetallic dispersoids are also formed. This
530 positively answers research question number 1.
- 531 • The formation of dispersoids occurs through homogeneous nucleation and growth directly from
532 the liquid phase. This is supported by evidence based on the spatial distribution of the
533 dispersoids as well as the diffusion distances of Y to grow to 100 nm or larger. This clarifies
534 research question number 2.
- 535 • The dispersoids remain chemically stable when subjected to thermal exposure during heat
536 treatment of powder or during sintering via FAST. Although formation of dispersoids is
537 achieved during the UA process, their number, size, and spatial distribution vary significantly
538 from one powder particle to another and strongly depend on the Y content present in each
539 powder particle at the time of atomization. The inhomogeneity in the dispersoid density across
540 different powder particles is attributed to the non-uniform Y concentration in the melt pool in
541 the UA device. Research question number 3 must be denied.
- 542 • Despite the substantially coarser grain and dispersoid sizes observed in the UA and FAST
543 powder compared to mechanically alloyed counterparts, the resulting hardness values are
544 comparable, albeit slightly lower by approximately 30–50 HV. The pronounced hardness
545 increase of about 80% between regions with low and high dispersoid densities underscores the
546 major impact of dispersoid density to strengthening. Overall, these findings demonstrate that
547 the present synthesis method offers a promising alternative to conventional mechanical alloying
548 for producing dispersion-strengthened ferritic alloys. This answers research question number 4.

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Conflict of Interest

555 The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data Availability Statement

556 The data presented in this study are available in KITopen at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17508782>
557 under CC BY-SA 4.0 license. Further information is available upon request with
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